

DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF STUDENTS IN THE ART OF ENGRAVING

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Abstract. *In this article, the main means of improving the activities of art and increasing the efficiency of the knowledge and skills provided in it is the use of a system of interdisciplinary connections in the study of academic subjects.*

Keywords: *applied art, pattern elements, manifested in the art of carving, in the art of engraving and ceramics.*

РАЗВИТИЕ ТВОРЧЕСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ СТУДЕНТОВ В ИСКУССТВЕ ГРАВИРОВКИ

Аннотация. *В данной статье основным средством совершенствования деятельности художественного искусства и повышения эффективности обеспечиваемых в нем знаний и умений является использование системы межпредметных и междисциплинарных связей при изучении учебных предметов.*

Ключевые слова: *прикладное искусство, элементы узора, проявляется в искусстве резьбы, в искусстве гравировки и керамики.*

INTRODUCTION

The most important task of professors-teachers is to give a comprehensive education to the younger generation, to educate them physically and spiritually mature people.

SH.M.Mirziyoyev

Naqsh - from Arabic means image, flower. This is an ornament created by repeating birds, animals, plants, geometric and other elements in a certain order. Patterns are made in various ways in carpentry, carving, embroidery, gold embroidery, pottery, jewelry, carpet weaving, wood carving, etc. For example: patterns are made by carving, drawing, satin stitch embroidery and other methods.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Artistic carving, which is an integral part of the Uzbek folk arts and crafts, with its antiquity and beauty, occupies a deep place in the hearts of people. Pattern compositions created from the arrangement of pattern elements add beauty to works of art. There are unique ways to create a composition in artistic carving, and the decoration of this pattern shows the imagination of the masters about beauty.

The works of Uzbek folk arts and crafts are a rich spiritual heritage and value not only today, but also for our future generations. Raising our youth to be comprehensively mature and able to meet the requirements of modernity is one of the urgent tasks of today. Currently, it is important to create new curricula, programs, manuals and textbooks in this area.

RESULTS

The role of composition in artistic carving. Artistic carving, which is one of the types of Uzbek folk arts and crafts, occupies an ever deeper place in the daily life of our people. The art of artistic carving, like other types of art, has its own composition rules, performance techniques and, of course, its own focus on color harmony. In addition to the elements of the pattern, decorations and various forms, the rules of composition, in artistic carving, the types of paints

used in it, their characteristics, color tone, harmony of colors, etc. are important. If we observe examples of patterns made by folk craftsmen, we will see that they are subject to the influence of one or another shade of color, that is, the color tint. Accordingly, patterns and patterned compositions are created in the medium of brown, airy, green and similar colors.

It should be remembered that when mixing some paints with each other, some precautions should be observed. Because if another color is mixed into the composition of dark paint, its color will also become darker. This, in turn, affects the level of color tones. In particular, the colors of patterns made with oil paints tend to blend and darken over time. If the patterns are intended for long-term storage, it is recommended to color them in light colors as much as possible.

DISCUSSION

The composition in artistic carving has its place and the stages of their compilation. Each structured composition is distinguished by its content, symbolic meanings, certain shapes and colors.

What to look for when creating a patterned composition?

- compliance with the ratio of pattern elements;
- creating a pattern composition suitable for the selected shape;
- exaggerate the form of tanoba in the main place;
- the image of such elements as flowers, branches, leaves in the composition in accordance with the movement of the branch.

Composition occupies a central place in the art of artistic carving. The content, meaning and essence of the pattern, in a word, beauty, depends on how and on what surface the composition is drawn. The naming of patterns and elements of the pattern deserves special attention; they are also called by the names of natural plants and objects, the master and the places where they were created. Among them: branch, tulip, flower pepper, shobarg, madohil, aigul, bafta, se barg, orange, "Mashkhadi", "Arabic", "Isfahani" and others. When creating patterned compositions, such rules as arrangement, symmetry, asymmetry, rhythmic repetition, finding the center, dynamic design, naturalness, beauty and harmony of colors are observed.

CONCLUSIONS

Artistic carving as a kind of folk arts and crafts has been an important part of Uzbek culture since ancient times. For many centuries, its artistic traditions have been created. Unlike all other types of art, patterns show a close connection between generations, the continuity of traditions. The traditions of painting were passed down from grandfather to father, from father to son as methods of teaching this art form. It is thanks to this continuity that the art of creating patterns has survived to this day. The best examples of the pattern are distinguished by the expediency and beauty of the forms, combined thanks to a rich creative imagination. This reflects the difference in the views of folk craftsmen on the environment. The play of lines in a pattern, like a melody in music, consists of "the great summation of people's life experience", like a song and a fairy tale.

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